

Session 9

Theatre 9

Automated monitoring of pig and chicken welfare at the slaughterhouse – tracing back to farm, transport and slaughter

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The EU aWISH project focuses on automated monitoring of animal-based indicators at slaughterhouses for documenting the welfare of broilers and pigs during each phase of production (farm/transport/slaughter). The project is centered around six European pilots – a slaughterhouse with a local research partner, associated farms and technology providers – where technologies are developed and validated. Pig pilots are located in Austria, the Netherlands, Serbia and Spain, broiler pilots in France and Poland. Eighteen technologies measure various indicators for pigs (ear lesions, skin lesions, tail length, tail lesions, blood parameters, stress vocalisation, tear staining, stunning effectiveness, environmental parameters, body weight, lung lesions, liver lesions, food consumption, meat quality) and broilers (hock burn, footpad lesions, catching damage, back scratches, stress vocalisations, activity, stunning effectiveness, environmental parameters, on-farm welfare assessment). Technologies are mainly installed in the slaughterhouse, some on-farm or on-truck, and some require human observations. An overview will be given of the installation of technologies, their status of development and which animal welfare aspect they are measuring. Via a data platform and online user interface, feedback on relevant individual and aggregated indicator scores is provided to those responsible per production phase. Data will also be used to document animal welfare improvements and their socio-economic and environmental impacts. This project will make a significant contribution to the objective assessment and improvement of pig and broiler welfare throughout Europe.

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Reliability of different behavioral tests as welfare indicator for dairy cows

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Human animal relationship (HAR) tests have the potential to reflect an important part of animal welfare on farm. To serve as welfare indicator, HAR-tests need to be reliable. Reliability of five different HAR-tests was therefore assessed by two trained observers who visited eleven commercial dairy farms in lower saxony. All farms were visited thrice, whereby visits were a week apart. At each visit, a novel object test (NOT: disinterested, interested, touched object, latency to contact), a voluntary human approach test (VHAT: latency to contact), a lie pass test (LP: disinterested, interested, stood up when passed) and an avoidance distance test (AD: flight reaction or touched by human, performed twice in different places) were conducted. Spearman correlation (rs) and intra class correlation (ICC) were used to assess the reliability of measurements between observers and between visits. Interobserver reliability of AD measurements were excellent (ICC and rS between 0.97 and 0.94). Reliability of NOT and LP categories varied from standing up (ICC and rS of 0.96) and touching the object (ICC 0.99, rS 0.98) to interest (0.92 and 0.90) in the NOT and (0.67 and 0.68) in the LP. ‘Disinterest’ was least reliable with rS of 0.45 in both tests and ICC of 0.65 in the NOT and 0.40 in the LP. Test-retest reliabilities were unacceptable (ICC and rS between 0 and 0.4). Low test-retest reliability can be explained by a small number of random animals chosen each visit. Exact influencing effects will be analyzed in the ongoing of the study.